

Interaction of Monoprotic Ligands with Cupric Ion in Various Mixed Aqueous Solvents.

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A new simpler method of calculation of free ligand concentration in complex equilibria in solutions has been applied to complex systems: Cu(II)-acetate, Cu(II)-thiophene-2-carboxylate, Cu(II)-salicylaldehyde in water, water-ethanol, water-dioxan, water-methanol, water-acetone, and water-iso propanol media (all 50% v/v). The formation constants are evaluated. Stabilities are found to be the lowest in water but the constants generally increase in the other solvents. Values of $\log \beta_n$ in 50% v/v mixed aqueous solvents do not show any linear relation with the reciprocal of the dielectric constant of the medium. But $\log \beta_n$ when plotted against $1/\epsilon$ for water-ethanol or water-dioxan mixed in various proportions does show linearity. In water-ethanol deviations occur for lower proportions of ethanol. $\log \beta_n$ in water-dioxan media shows linearity against $1/\epsilon$ for the concentrations of dioxan studied. Thermodynamic stability constant for Cu(II)-acetate system in water-ethanol medium (50% v/v) is evaluated: $\log \beta_1 = 2.82$; $\log \beta_2 = 5.18$. Thermodynamic parameters are also measured corresponding to complexes ML ($\Delta H^\circ = 3248$ K Cals/mole; $\Delta S^\circ = 23.207$ Cals/degree/mole) and ML₂ ($\Delta H^\circ = 14.617$ K. Cals/mole; $\Delta S^\circ = 72.347$ Cals/degree/mole).

WHEN the metal complexes are formed in solution with monoprotic ligands the concentration of the free ligand can be calculated with the help of a simple equation¹.

$$[L] = (T_L^0 - \bar{n} T_M^0) (1 - \bar{n}_A) \frac{V^0}{V^0 + V'''} \quad (1)$$

where T_L^0 and T_M^0 are the initial concentrations of ligand and metal ion respectively. V^0 is the initial volume, \bar{n} and \bar{n}_A are metal-ligand and proton-ligand formation functions respectively and V''' is the volume of alkali added for metal titration.

Validity of application of this simple expression of $[L]$, which does not involve $C\beta_1^H$ (proton-ligand formation constant) or $[H^+]$ has been demonstrated in a previous communication². In that paper, the method of calculation was shown with the systems: Cu(II)-acetate; Cu(II)-thiophene-2-carboxylate and Cu(II)-salicylaldehyde in water, water-dioxan and water-ethanol media. As the method offers an opportunity to study such metal-ligand interactions in any mixed aqueous system with the help of the simple expression for $[L]$, we have extended the study of these complex systems to three other solvents v.z. water-methanol, water-acetone and water-isopropanol. These organic solvents are freely miscible with water.

All the results from the study of the six solvents including water are combined here to make a comparative study.

Apart from the measurement of stability constants in various mixed-aqueous media, we were also interested

to find if there is any relation between the $\log \beta_n$ values and the dielectric constants of the media.

In 1920 Born³ established the linearity of relation between the dissociation constants of acids and bases and the inverse of the dielectric constants of the medium. Turian⁴ and Popa et al.^{5,6} extended this theory to complex systems. Molina et al.⁷ investigated AgClO₄-pyridine system in water-ethanol media mixed in various proportions. They also found linear relations between $\log \beta_n$ values and the inverse of dielectric constants of the medium ($1/\epsilon$).

Experimental

Materials and methods are already reported². All the solvents were of A. R./G. R. quality. They were dehydrated and distilled before use. Irving and Rossotti's⁸ method of pH titration any method of least squares for calculation were followed as before. For Cu(II)-salicylaldehyde system appropriate equations¹ were employed. Dielectric constants of the solvents were obtained or calculated from the values reported by Åkerlöf⁹ and Conway¹⁰. The actual pH in water-methanol, water-isopropanol and water-acetone media are determined experimentally as described before².

Results and Discussion

Values of the formation constants for the complex systems in 50% v/v mixed aqueous solvents are shown in Table 1. Dielectric constants (and the values of their reciprocal) are also shown in the table. For the metal ligand systems no linear relation could be observed (Fig. not shown) between the values of $\log \beta_n$

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TABLE 1—FORMATION CONSTANTS OF METAL-LIGAND COMPLEX SYSTEMS IN VARIOUS MIXED AQUEOUS SOLVENTS (5% v/v) AT 30° ± 0.1° WITH 0.1 M NaClO₄ IONIC STRENGTH.

Solvent	Reciprocal of the 1/ε dielectric constant	Cu(II)-acetate		Cu(II)-thiophene-2-carboxylate		Cu(II)-salicylaldehyde	
		log K ₁	log K ₂	log K ₁	log K ₂	log K ₁	log K ₂
Water	0.01303	1.76	2.17	(1.90) ^a 2.43	—	5.12	5.82
Water-dioxan	0.03125	3.13	2.48	2.61	2.52	5.51	5.96
Water-ethanol	0.01941	2.73	2.73	2.07	2.65	5.56	4.27
Water-methanol	0.0178	2.16	2.43	2.72	—	5.51	4.78
Water-acetone	0.0198	2.80	2.29	2.90	2.21	5.32	5.90
Water-isopropanol	0.0219	2.27	2.57	2.60	—	5.97	5.61

^aAt 25° and zero ionic strength¹³.

and the reciprocals of the dielectric constant (1/ε) of the media, for all the solvents including water. For Cu (II)-acetate system it can be roughly said that the formation constants increase as the dielectric constants decrease. It is possible that the ionic part of the metal ligand interaction could be influenced like this by the dielectric property of the medium. Absence of correlation in general signifies that each solvent has its characteristic role (i.e. solvation energy etc.) in the interactions. Abnormal cases of K₂ > K₁ are observed, for Cu(II) acetate system in water, water-methanol and water-isopropanol; for Cu(II)-thiophene-2-carboxylate system in water ethanol. For Cu(II)-thiophene 2-carboxylate.

system K₂ is not observed in water-isopropanol, water-methanol and pure water media.

In case of Cu(II)-salicylaldehyde system the formation constants are calculated on the basis

$$K_1 = \frac{[ML][H]}{[M][HL]}; K_2 = \frac{[ML_2][H]}{[ML][HL]}$$

In this system also the log β_n does not show any linearity when plotted against 1/ε. Reversal of order i.e. K₂ > K₁ is found in the water-isopropanol medium.

TABLE 2—FORMATION CONSTANTS OF Cu(II)-ACETATE COMPLEX IN ETHANOL-WATER AND DIOXAN-WATER MEDIA AT 30°.

Solvent	NaClO ₄ concentration	Reciprocal of dielectric constant (1/ε)	log K ₁	log K ₂
Ethanol-water 50%, v/v	0.1M	0.01941	2.73	2.54
40%, v/v	"	0.0175	2.55	2.26
30% v/v	"	0.0160	2.42	2.26
20%, v/v	"	0.0148	2.53	—
10%, v/v	"	0.0138	2.31	—
0% v/v	"	0.0130	1.76	2.17
Dioxan-water 50%, v/v	0.1M	0.03125	3.13	2.48
40% v/v	"	0.0246	2.98	2.15
30% v/v	"	0.0202	2.74	—
Ethanol-water 50%, v/v	0.1M	0.01941	2.73	2.54
"	0.2M	do	2.65	2.67
"	0.35M	do	2.51	2.91
Ethanol-water 50%, v/v at 20°	0.1M	do	2.65	2.26

The $\log \beta_n$ values are further measured in water-ethanol and water-dioxan media mixed in various proportions (Table 2). Proportions of ethanol in water are 50%, 40%, 30%, 20%, 10% and 0% (water) v/v, these correspond to 43.82%, 34.43%, 25.05%, 16.37%, 8.01% and 0% (water) w/w. Proportions of dioxan in water were 50%, 40% and 30% (v/v) which correspond to 50.84%, 40.81% and 30.71% w/w. The values of $\log \beta_n$ are plotted against $1/\epsilon$. The curves are shown in Fig. 1 and Fig. 2. The curve I for $\log \beta_1$ in Fig. 1 shows linearity for volume percentages of ethanol equal to 30% and above. It is evident that for still higher concentrations of ethanol (above 50% v/v), good linear relation is expected. $\log \beta_1$ for 20%, 10% and 0% ethanol deviate considerably from linearity. On introduction of the effect of dilution, that is by plotting $\log \beta_1 [H_2O]$ vs $1/\epsilon$ as proposed by Yasuda¹¹ and Shedlovky¹² it is found that although the straight line is further smoothed the deviations remain. The point for pure water medium ($1/\epsilon=0.013$) is obviously very much off the line. In 20% and 10% ethanol-water the second complex is not formed, as it is evident from the Y/X line and so the stability of the 1:1 complexes are comparatively higher. This may be a reason for deviation from linearity. It also appears that introduction of the organic solvent in low concentrations produces some drastic change in the solvent characteristics and when the concentration increases the change becomes gradual. Therefore $\log \beta_1$ which is evidently related to the dielectric constant of the medium tends to show linearity against $1/\epsilon$ at higher concentrations, $\log \beta_2$ values (Curve II, Fig. 1) also falls on a good straight line.

Similar studies with the same complex system in water dioxan media in 30%, 40% and 50% v/v dioxan, once again reveals linear relations (Fig. 2, Curve I). $\log \beta_2$ is not obtained for 30% dioxan. A straight line (Curve II, Fig. 2) is however drawn between the two points which indicates the expected line for higher concentrations of dioxan.

Fig. 1. Relation between $\log \beta_n$ and inverse of dielectric constant ($1/\epsilon$) of water-ethanol media (Curve I for $\log \beta_1$, Curve II for $\log \beta_2$).

Fig. 2. Relation between $\log \beta_n$ and inverse of dielectric constant ($1/\epsilon$) of water-dioxan media (Curve I for $\log \beta_1$ and Curve II for $\log \beta_2$).

Fig. 3. Plot of stoichiometric stability constants, against concentration of $NaClO_4$ in 50% v/v water-ethanol medium.

The thermodynamic stability constant for Cu(II)-acetate system is obtained in 50% v/v water-ethanol by measuring the constants at 0.1M, 0.2M and 0.35M $NaClO_4$. These values (Table 2) are plotted against the concentration of $NaClO_4$ [Fig. 3]. The points fall on a straight line. On extrapolation to zero ionic strength the values of the thermodynamic constants are found. The values are

$$\log K_1 = 2.82 ; \log K_2 = 2.36 ; \log \beta_2 = 5.18$$

For the above system (Cu (II)-acetate) the thermodynamic parameters are calculated by measuring the formation constants at two temperatures, 30° and 20° (Table 2). The values of ΔH° and ΔS° are calculated

by the usual methods. These are given below :

Complex	ΔH° OK.Cals/mole	ΔS° Cals/degree/mole
ML(β_1)	3.248	23.207
ML ₂ (β_2)	14.617	72.347

The results indicate that the interaction is endothermic but the entropy change is favourable for the reaction.

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